

COMPLEX ASSESSMENT OF CHILDREN'S PHYSICAL, MENTAL AND
SEXUAL DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation. A comprehensive assessment of the physical development of children requires extensive comprehensive examination using various methods, taking into account the individual characteristics of the younger generation. In assessing the physical development of children, it is generally accepted that it is necessary to take into account not only regional characteristics, but also the type of Housing (city, village). The nature of the interaction of climatogeographic and socio-economic factors in urban and rural areas is not the same, therefore, children who live permanently in rural areas may differ from urban children in terms of their physical health, somatic indicators and functional characteristics.

Keywords: children, characteristics, future games, rapid growth, anthropometric indicators, education, healthy.

Introduction. Physical development (PD) is one of the criteria of human health and a demographic indicator of the health of the nation. FR is a natural process of changing the morphological and functional characteristics of the body, closely related to a person's age, gender, state of health, hereditary factors and living conditions. At the turn of the century, Academician Yu.E. Veltishchev (2000) outlined the range of main problems of modern pediatrics, which are still relevant today: a progressive decline in the level of children's health, an increase in the number of children with chronic pathology, including the number of children with disabilities, as well as a decrease in indicators of physical development and biological maturity among adolescents. To correct medical control methods when solving existing problems, the need to develop complexes of biometric indicators (indicators of RF, neuropsychological development, average values of peripheral blood indicators, humoral and cellular immunity systems) for each critical period (or

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stage) of children's development is indicated. Children of preschool age gradually learn to work together in a team, compromise with others on the basis of regular games. Each game with rules has its own idea and meaning. The correct implementation of the rules during the game is determined by the grades "correct" or "incorrect", "the rule of the game has been violated". Children learn self-control during play. Of course, at the end of each game, the result should be discussed by the coach, the goal, rules and results should be paid attention to. At the end of the game, encouraging the participants and praising the active participants will ensure the effective passage of future games. All the above-mentioned types of games with rules have their own rules according to the content. They have the following characteristics:

- the existence of a game task performed through game actions;
- actions and relations of players are guided by rules;
- presence of rules and ready content in the game;
- the educational content of the game is embodied in the events of the game actions, which do not appear as an independent task for children.

To determine the level of physical development and harmony of children, the most common method based on centile tables is used. This method is very easy to use, because it does not require any calculations and allows to assess the individual development rate of the child during ontogeny. Since the most rapid growth and development of the child takes place in the womb, factors specific to this period play a very important role. If during this period there are disturbances and deficiencies in the nutrition of the fetus, then the child may have a lack of growth and/or a low body weight. Body size in boys depends on how the pregnancy and delivery process went (big boys are born when the pregnancy and delivery process is usually normal). Maternal smoking during pregnancy leads to an increase in body fat in girls between 3 and 7 years of age, as well as a decrease in the size of the body skeleton. Children born to mothers who were sick during pregnancy are significantly behind in physical development compared to children born to mothers who spent the pregnancy period healthy. Obesity in women during pregnancy is one of the early factors in the development of overweight in children, and increases obesity and health problems in children of adulthood. When the mother becomes obese during pregnancy, the fetus also begins to overeat. Both overweight and underweight babies are known to increase the risk of obesity later in life.

Conclusion. Thus, each age period is characterized by certain anatomical and physiological characteristics, on the basis of which the organization of the daily routine, care, upbringing, nutrition, organization of the educational process, measures for the prevention of diseases, preventive measures, as well as the daily

routine of children it is necessary to solve the issues of organizing the order. as well as methods and forms of physical education and health related to sports. Many authors believe that for a general assessment of a child's physical development, it is enough to observe changes in 4 main anthropometric indicators: DT, MT, OGK and OG. The main part of research confirms that the change of physical development indicators of children and adolescents compared to standard indicators depends on the level of natural-climatic, ethnic, environmental conditions and anthropogenic load. The studied literature confirms the need to develop and regularly review regional standards for the physical development of children in different periods of life. Monitoring of regional standards of children's physical development in important periods of development should be taken into account by pediatricians and specialists in the field of physical education and sports when planning activities with children and dosing physical activity, as well as choosing sports and sports orientation. It is very important to pay attention to the smooth process of the child's introduction to sports activities. The first years should be focused on the general physical fitness of children, gradually increasing the loads. This is the best way to do sports. Monitoring of the health status of young athletes should be carried out by a pediatrician on an ongoing basis. It is the doctor who is focused on the training of healthy athletes who can give physiologically based recommendations to teachers-coaches on increasing the number of loads, so that their volume and intensity help to develop a healthy body, and not only achieve success. high results at the limit of physical capabilities.

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